

Caries Excavation; Current Concepts and Techniques

Anjali Kumari Annu¹
Samridhi Singh²
Navpreet Kaur³

Intern¹
Department of Pediatric & Preventive Dentistry
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Intern²
Department of Pediatric & Preventive Dentistry
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Associate Professor³
Department of Pediatric & Preventive Dentistry
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Submitted 11 february 2026
Accepted 12 february 2026
Published xx xxx xxxx

<p>Access this Article Online Website: www.healtalk.in</p> <p>DOI</p>	<p>Quick Response Code</p>
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Abstract

Dental caries is a disease and the carious lesion is the disease's consequence and manifestation it's signs and symptoms. Carious lesion management is used to control the disease symptoms at the tooth level, whereas dental caries management is used to control the disease symptoms at the patient level using preventive and noninvasive methods. While it is impossible to link the clinical signs of carious lesions to their visual appearance, we have been able to do so indirectly, based on disease clinical outcomes (soft, leathery, firm, and hard dentine). The following are the methods for removing carious tissue: 1) selective carious tissue removal, including selective removal to soft dentine and selective removal to firm dentine; 2) stepwise removal, including stage 1 selective removal to soft dentine and stage 2 selective removal to firm dentine 6 to 12 months later; and 3) Previously known as full caries removal, nonselective removal to hard dentine (technique no longer recommended).

Introduction

Dental caries is one of the most commonly occurring disease in the world, and its treatment is expensive both financially and biologically (dental pain infection and tooth loss). Non operative therapies (plaque and diet control, fluoride application) are important for preventing caries progression. However, operative dentistry (removal of carious tissue and placement of restorations) has a role to play in plaque control and restoration of tooth form and function.

Traditionally, the operative therapy for dental caries was to totally eliminate all remnants of carious tissue, allowing the restoration margins to rest on sound tooth structure. The bacteria infected carious tissue is excavated using a high/low speed bur or hand excavation devices (Kidd 1998) Dental caries has been classified histologically and clinically into two layers: the outer zone (stains with caries detector dyes) where the dentine is highly demineralized, the collagen denatured, and heavily infected with bacteria (often referred to as the infected zone), and the inner zone (does not stain with a caries detector dye) where the dentine is demineralized, but the collagen is intact and minimally infected (often referred to as the caries affected zone) (Fusayama 1972) Traditionally, during cavity preparation all caries remains were eliminated (Black GV 1908). Contemporary cavity preparation, on the other hand, clears caries from the cavity's periphery while

merely removing the outside caries infected zone pulpally. Dentists have accepted and practised this type of treatment for years. However, such a restorative technique has a lot of negative implications.

- 1. Entry to the restorative cycle:** While caries treatment and restoration provide a short-term advantage of eliminating diseased, soft demineralized dentine and restoring tooth shape, they cannot be considered a long-term remedy because the vast majority of restorations placed by dentists are replacement restorations (Elderton 1990) Individual teeth are frequently re-restored due to restorative material failure, new caries next to the restoration, and tooth structure failure due to weakening.
- 2. RDT (remaining dentine thickness) reduction:** When a cavity is prepared and a restoration is placed, the cavity size increases, and the RDT (remaining dentine thickness) between the cavity floor and the pulp decreases. The RDT has been demonstrated to be the most important variable in cavity preparation that affects pulpal health (Murray 2003)⁴.

How to Cite This Article : Annu et al. -

3. Pulpal exposure: At its most extreme, caries removal in dentine lesions can lead to exposure of vital pulp tissue. Such exposures in symptomless teeth have traditionally been treated with a direct pulp capping or a pulpotomy. When these procedures are employed to treat pulps exposed by dental trauma, they have a high success rate (Cvek 1978). However, outcomes are poor following carious exposures (where the pulp is more likely to be damaged due to diseased dentine) (Al Hiyasat 2006, ; Barthel 2000).

In an effort to address and limit the negative repercussions of restorative treatment, more conservative procedures known as minimal intervention strategies for caries control have been established and are becoming more frequently recognised. Minimal intervention can be defined in a variety of ways, although it typically entails total caries eradication. It is uncertain whether the traditional approach to caries removal is necessary and this dogma has been challenged by a number of procedures and studies (Kidd 2004), where partial or no caries removal was carried out (Thompson 2008)⁷.

Discussion

Dental caries is the name of the disease and the carious lesion is the consequence and manifestation of the disease.

Caries Management and Carious Lesion Management

Caries management is a term to describe the actions taken at a patient level, that includes

1. Plaque control
2. Tooth brushing instruction,
3. Fluoride application,
4. Dietary interventions
5. Behavior change techniques

Carious lesion management means any procedure that involves doing something to an established, non cleansable carious lesion to stop its progression. This might involve removing *none, some, or all of the carious tissues* from a non cleansable lesion.

Guiding Principles of Caries Tissue Removal

1. Preservation of dental tissues
2. Maintenance of pulpal health
3. Avoidance of pulp exposure
4. Avoidance of dental anxiety (often considered particularly important in children but should be considered for all patients)
5. Provision of sound cavity margins to achieve a peripheral seal

Definitions for Different Clinical Presentations of Dentine: Soft, Leathery, Firm, and Hard (Fig:1)

Soft Dentine: When a hard instrument is forced against it, soft dentine deforms and can be easily scooped up (e.g., with a sharp hand excavator) with minimal force.

Leathery Dentine: Despite the fact that it does not deform when an instrument is put on it, leathery dentine can be easily lifted with little effort. Leathery and firm dentine may have minimal difference, with leathery occupying a middle ground between soft and hard dentine.

Firm Dentine: Firm dentine is physically resistant to hand excavation, and it must be lifted with the use of an instrument.

Hard Dentine: To engage hard dentine, a pushing force with a hard instrument is required, and only a sharp cutting edge or a bur will be able to lift it. When a straight probe is passed across the dentine, a scratchy sound called "cri dentinaire" can be heard.

Fig 1: Diagrammatic representation of the carious lesion (after Ogawa et al. 1983)

Different Approaches For Carious Tissue Removal

1. Complete excavation or complete caries removal, also known as non selective removal of hard dentine, is no longer suggested as a method for removing carious tissue. It is a method of removing carious tissue that was once regarded acceptable but is now considered overtreatment. The goal was to remove soft carious tissue in order to reach hard dentine that looked and felt like healthy dentine in all areas of the cavity, including the pulp. Complete caries excavation in the pulpal area is defined by Bjørndal et al. (2010), as "leaving only central yellowish or greyish firm dentin (equivalent to the hardness of sound dentin, as judged by mild probing)". However, for deep caries lesions (reaching into the inner pulpal third of dentine on radiograph), Complete caries excavation, on the other hand, is now thought to be likely to result in tooth detriment through pulp exposure specifically, indirect pulp damage from irritation passing through the thin, remaining dentine thickness or from unnecessarily weakening the tooth's structural integrity (Rickett 2013)⁹. This method isn't advised any longer.
2. Stepwise Removal: Stepwise caries removal includes removal of carious lesion in two stages:
 - a. Stage 1: Selective removal to soft dentine. Stage 1 has the same carious tissue removal goals as selective removal to soft dentine, but with enough carious tooth tissue removed to construct a durable restoration while avoiding pulp exposure. The cavity's periphery should be firm, resembling sound dentine in appearance and feel. A temporary restoration is put with a restorative material that can last up to 12 months.
 - b. Stage 2: 6 to 12 months later, selective dentine removal. The stage 2 pathway involves selective removal to firm dentine with placement of a definitive restoration aimed for permanence, should be pursued after the removal of this interim restoration. 2-step excavation is the name given to this method.
3. Selective Removal of Carious Tissue: Different excavation criteria are utilised when examining the cavity's periphery to the area in close proximity to the pulp in selective removal. To ensure the optimum adhesive seal, the cavity's periphery should be encircled by "sound" enamel. When scraping the surface with a sharp hand excavator or dental probe, the peripheral dentine should be firm and have similar tactile characteristics to sound dentine, such as a scratching sounds.
 - a. Selective removal to soft dentine: In deep lesions, selective removal of soft dentine means that soft carious dentine is left in the pulpal aspect of the cavity. To get the finest adhesive seal, peripheral enamel and dentine should be firm at the end of

excavation. Partial caries, 1-step, ultraconservative, or incomplete caries eradication are all terms used to describe this procedure. Check the softness/hardness of the remaining dentine with a sharp hand excavator; keep in mind that soft dentine will deform when an instrument is pushed against it, and lifting it will need little power. It should be used for deep carious lesions that extend beyond the inner (pulpal) third or quarter of the dentine radiographically; the major goal is to avoid exposing or irritating the pulp, as long as no clinical indications of pulp inflammation are present.

- b. Selective removal to firm dentine. In selective removal to firm dentine, the goal is to excavate the pulpal aspect of the cavity to leathery or firm dentine (physically resistive to the hand excavator). In this method contaminated carious lesion but not the demineralized dentine, which can be remineralized is aimed at being removed. It is acknowledged that there are no simple or frequently utilised methods for determining when contaminated tissue has been removed and when what is visible in the cavity is just demineralized dentine. However, the tactile sensation of hitting firm dentine on the pulpal floor, rather than aiming for hard dentine, is probably the best guide that can be offered, despite being somewhat subjective.
4. No Removal: No Dentine Carious Tissue Removal: There are a number of techniques that do not require the removal of dentine carious tissue. Despite the fact that different approaches are employed to do this, the goal is the same: to control the carious lesion without removing any of the damaged dentine tissue. Under the heading of "no carious tissue removal," the following treatments have been included.
 - a. Sealant materials made of resin or glass ionomer. Over enamel and dentine carious lesions, therapeutic sealant materials (resin or high viscosity glass ionomer cements) can be used. Mechanical qualities are limited for filling and covering microcavities in enamel, especially with unfilled resin. The ability of the materials to resist stresses occlusally when there is a significant quantity of soft dentine beneath the weaker enamel (the "trampoline" effect) is also a theoretical problem. As a result, the scope of lesions where these materials can be used may be limited, pending evidence, to lesions that are confined (on a radiograph) to the outside third of the dentine.
 - b. The Hall technique :This is a technique for primary molars that involves the placement of a prefabricated stainless steel crown on the tooth to seal dentine carious lesions. The crown is bonded over a primary molar tooth and carious lesion with glass ionomer cement, with no tooth preparation or carious lesion removal. Approximal lesions are the most common indications. The crown efficiently seals the dentine carious lesion and slows or stops it from progressing to the dental pulp, allowing the primary molar to exfoliate without pain and infection.
 - c. Nonrestorative cavity control: By successfully initiating an intensive preventive programme that involves plaque removal via tooth brushing with fluoridated toothpaste and/or application of fluoride varnish, a cleansable cavity can be achieved. In the case of a carious lesion, it may be necessary to change the shape of the cavity by opening the cavity edges in order to make it cleanable, which would necessitate some operative, but not restorative, intervention. These techniques are most commonly used on primary teeth, but they can also be useful in the permanent dentition, such as in root caries.
 - d. Application of SDF: It is a safe and effective non restorative treatment option available that aids in caries arrest.

How the intervention might work (stepwise excavation, partial caries removal and no caries removal)

Sealing diseased demineralised dentine into a cavity with a repair that produces a good peripheral seal deprives bacteria of a source of food. The quantity of bacteria decreases, and the caries process halts (Handelman 1976). Not only does the number of bacteria decrease, but the microbial variety also decreases. Only microorganisms that can break down the fluid glycoproteins in pulpal tissue can survive (Paddick 2005)¹⁰. A number of other clinical trials, such as those reported by Fejerskov¹¹ and Kidd (2008) and Thompson (2008⁷), have looked into and supported this notion.

Within sealed carious dentine, a gradual drop in the number of organisms and a shift to a less cariogenic microflora leads to a steady reduction in lesion activity and therefore lesion progression. This gives the pulp-dentine complex enough time to lay down tertiary and peritubular dentine, resulting in tubular sclerosis and lowering the permeability of the remaining dentine.

This decrease in pulpal exudate depletes the bacteria's nutritional source even more.

The provisional restoration is removed after a period of time in stepwise caries excavation to allow for additional caries eradication. The tertiary dentine, which has already had time to form, protects the dental pulp even more and minimises the chance of pulpal exposure. Managing carious pulpal exposures using a direct pulp capping approach is associated with a poor prognosis for keeping a vital pulp (AlHiyasat 2006⁵; Barthel 2000), so avoiding pulp exposure is crucial to the tooth's long-term success. Partial caries or no dentinal caries removal techniques also have the potential to reduce cavity size and hence preserve tooth structure. The restoration, however does not have a solid base as a result of such procedures. The long-term influence of this on restoration longevity is still being discussed, albeit it may not be as significant for primary teeth due to their short lifespans.

Important Systematic Reviews Comparing Different Caries Excavation Techniques

Thompson V, Craig RG, Curro FA, Green WS, Ship JA in 2008⁷, did a systematic review on Treatment of Deep carious lesion by complete excavation or partial removal. A search of five internet databases for research on partial versus complete excision of carious lesions generated 1,059 results, of which the authors determined 23 to be relevant. Out of 23, three were randomised controlled trials, one of which followed patients for ten years, give solid support for the wisdom of leaving infected dentin in place, as removing it would expose the pulp. Several other investigations have shown that after cariogenic bacteria are removed from their source of nutrition by restoring adequate integrity, they either die or become dormant, posing no damage to the dentition's health. Hence it was concluded that removing all vestiges of infected dentin from lesions approaching the pulp is not required for caries management.

Ferreira JM, Pinheiro SL, Sampaio FC, de Menezes VA in 2012¹² did a systematic review on Caries removal in primary teeth. Abstracts of English-language papers published between 2000 and 2010, as well as randomised clinical trials addressing the total, partial, and or nonmechanical removal of carious tissue in primary teeth, were searched in the Medline, Cochrane, and PubMed databases. After reading the abstracts of 151 articles, 6 references were chosen for further investigation and out of them 3 papers were identified as potentially relevant to this study. After analysis it was suggested that minimally invasive procedures for

dental tissue are viable choices for stopping caries lesions. Partial or non mechanical removal of carious tissue favors the arrest of dental caries lesions.¹²

Aiem E, Joseph C, Garcia A, Smail-Faugeron V, Muller-Bolla M₁₃ did a systematic review on Caries removal strategies for deep carious lesions in primary teeth in year 2020. Authors conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials, the researchers aimed to compare the efficacy of three caries removal techniques complete caries removal (CCR), selective caries removal (SCR), and stepwise caries removal (SWR) for deep carious lesions in vital temporary teeth (RCTs). Up until May 31, 2019, electronic databases (PubMed MEDLINE, Cochrane Library, EMBASE) were searched for related references. Pulp exposure, pulpo-periodontal problems, and restorative failures are all possible outcomes were assessed. In comparison to CCR, there was a lower risk of pulp exposure after SCR (OR: 0.10, 95 percent CI [0.04, 0.25]) or SWR (OR: 0.20, 95 percent CI [0.09, 0.44]). In an intention to treat analysis, there was a greater probability of composite restorative failure following SCR compared to CCR (OR: 2.61, 95 percent CI [1.05, 6.49]). When comparing SCR to CCR or SWR, the risk of clinical or radiographic pulpoperiodontal complications failure remained unchanged. Hence it was concluded that SCR and SWR may have a lower risk of pulp exposure than CCR. To choose amongst these three caries removal procedures for deep carious lesions in vital temporary teeth, RCTs with lower risk of bias, higher power, and longer follow-up are necessary.

Conclusion

The old principal of GV Black of extension for prevention is long forgotten and modified. Modern operative dentistry is not just limited to drilling and filling. The continuous advancements in researches and materials have made minimally invasive treatment of carious teeth practically attainable. Due to the risk of pulpal exposure, complete caries removal (CCR) and stepwise caries removal (SWR) are no longer indicated in primary teeth. When compared to CCR and SWR, several systematic reviews have found that selective caries removal (SCR) has a similar outcome in terms of clinical and radiographic pulpo-periodontal problems, although there is a much lower chance of pulp exposure. Further RCTs with higher power are still needed to demonstrate conclusively the routine suitability of SCR which is already recommended in the permanent teeth.¹³

References

1. Kidd EAM, Smith BGN, Pickard HM. *Pickard's Manual of Operative Dentistry*. 7th Edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998.
2. Fusayama T, Terashima S. Differentiation of two layers of carious dentin by staining. *Journal of Dental Research* 1972;51(3):866.
3. Elderton RJ. Clinical studies concerning rerestitution of teeth. *Advances in Dental Research* 1990;4:49.
4. Murray PE, Smith AJ, Windsor LJ, Mjör IA. Remaining dentine thickness and human pulp responses. *International Endodontic Journal* 2003;36(1):33-43.
5. Al Hiyasat AS, Barrieshi Nusair KM, Al Omari MA. The radiographic outcomes of direct pulp capping procedures performed by dental students: a retrospective study. *Journal of the American Dental Association* 2006;137(12):1699-705.
6. Kidd EA. How 'clean' must a cavity be before restoration?. *Caries Research* 2004;38(3):305-13.
7. Thompson VP, Craig RG, Curro FA, Green WS, Ship JA. Treatment of deep carious lesions by complete excavation or partial removal: a critical review. *Journal of the American Dental Association* 2008;139(6):705-12.
8. Bjørndal L, Reit C, Bruun G, Markvart M, Kjøeldgaard M, Näsman P, Thordrup M, Dige I, Nyvad B, Fransson H, et al. 2010. Treatment of deep caries lesions in adults: randomized clinical trials comparing stepwise vs. direct complete excavation, and direct pulp capping vs. partial pulpotomy. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 118(3):290-297.
9. Ricketts D, Lamont T, Innes NP, Kidd E, Clarkson JE. 2013. Operative caries management in adults and children. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 3:CD003808.
10. Paddick JS, Brailsford SR, Kidd EA, Beighton D. 2005. Phenotypic and genotypic selection of microbiota surviving under dental restorations. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 71(5): 2467-2472.
11. Fejerskov O, Larsen MJ. 2015. Demineralization and remineralisation: the key to understanding clinical manifestations of dental caries. In: Fejerskov O, Nyvad B, Kidd E, editors. *Dental caries: the disease and its clinical management*. 3rd ed. Oxford (UK): Wiley Blackwell. p. 160-169. 14
12. Ferreira JM, Pinheiro SL, Sampaio FC, de Menezes VA. 2012. Caries removal in primary teeth: a systematic review. *Quintessence Int*. 43(1): e9-e15.
13. Aiem E, Joseph C, Garcia A, Smail-Faugeron V, Muller-Bolla M. Caries removal strategies for deep carious lesions in primary teeth: Systematic review. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2020 Jul; 30(4): 392-404.